

MODERN METHODS OF MOVING GOODS IN RETAIL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. *This article analyzed the methods of selling goods in retail trade, retail trade, the types of activities aimed at moving goods and trademarks, and made the necessary proposals.*

Keywords: *retail, trade, trade aftomati, Trade marketing, assortment, merchandising, brand brand.*

Retail trade involves entrepreneurial activities that are directly related to the sale and service of goods to the population. Retail trade participates in the formation of the assortment of goods. Provides customers with information about the quality indicators of goods. Performs the functions of storing goods, additional work, setting prices and others. As a result, it performs purchase and Sale work with the final consumers of the goods. Retail trade stands by the form of ownership, method and service.

Types of retail firms differ by 4 criteria:

1. Equipment of the store.
2. Customer service level.
3. Assortment of goods.
4. In trade, the service differs in character.

– In the general unified chain of commodity movement, the technology processes of retail trade are an important link. Because in the process of delivery of folk consumer goods from a manufacturing enterprise to consumers, the most necessary conditions for the selection of goods and meeting the growing needs of the population for these goods should be created at the same retail enterprises. The quality of providing sales services to the population, that is, the culture of trade, depends on the level of Organization of technology processes in retail trade, in particular, the sale of goods, due to which the entire operational activity of retail enterprises is subordinated to this task.

- Currently, the following methods of selling goods are used in retail trade:
- sale of goods by counter;
 - selling the goods in a way that the buyer serves himself;
 - sell by spreading the Goods Open;
 - sale showing goods;
 - sale of goods according to the order of the population.

Selling goods over the counter is a typical way of selling goods, in which almost all the main elements of the process of servicing buyers, namely, the work of displaying goods and introducing them to its assortment, making calculations and transferring the paid goods, is performed by the seller standing near the counter.

Buyers can freely go to the walls of the sales area or near all the goods picked up in the middle in the way of selling goods on the basis of self-service, independently select and put them

in inventory corzines or strollers themselves, the payment for the goods is paid at the only settlement place at the exit from the store.

When selling goods with open spread, buyers can easily go to the seller's workplace and get acquainted independently, with the advice and help of the seller, choosing the goods they need.

When selling goods with open spread, as in the way in which buyers serve themselves, the goods are released in full readiness for sale to the sales Hall.

In the conditions of the sales method, indicating samples of goods, the buyer, depending on the samples placed in the sales area, chooses the goods he needs independently or with the help of the seller, after paying for it, receives the corresponding goods directly from the store or orders an expedited home for an additional fee. This method can be organized in the sale of large volumes – furniture, refrigerator, washing machine, sewing machine, electric light, snacks.

In the way of selling the goods according to the order of the population, the buyer places a pre-order in the Order Department of the store or at the place of acceptance of the order established at the place of industrial enterprise, construction, institution, field shed, residence. This goods are taken from the store or delivered to the customer's home or to another place specified in the order.

This method can be used in the sale of all food products, as well as in the sale of goods of a complex assortment through shops located in rural settlements inside and trading in goods that are in demand on a daily basis.

One of the advanced trading methods is trading through vending machines. Vending machines occupy an important place in ensuring the socio-economic efficiency of trade, that is, reducing consumer costs in trade is important in conditions when the consumer is a hockey player.

In the current conditions, the use of vending machines with a modern design is an important issue. One of the modern methods of trading is trading marketing. In Trad-marketing, several main tools are distinguished:

- sales promotion;
- special events;
- merchandising.

Merchandising (visual. merchandising) - the part of the marketing process that determines the methodology for selling a brand in a store. Merchandising is a complex of marketing activities that is carried out in commercial premises, first of all, in the conduct of retail trade, and is aimed at creating a favorable situation that will bring the buyer to the goods and ensure the maximum probability of purchase. It is envisaged that merchandising will determine the set of goods sold in a retail store, methods for placing goods, provide them with promotional materials and price indicators.

Merchandising is a type of activity used by large retail enterprises (supermarkets, hypermarkets), aimed at moving goods and trademarks in the regional market, the reason for its occurrence is the lack of qualified sellers. The main requirements for its application are considered:

the enterprise must always have a full range of goods;

special equipment is necessary: Organization of trading halls, including special refrigeration units, placement of equipment throughout the hall, sound environment in the trading hall, color of walls, lighting, etc.;

within the enterprise, as a rule, small points of sale with better quality and more expensive goods should be established;

the placement of goods should be carried out in such a way that the consumer should be forced to walk as much as possible through the trading hall, practically not resorting to the help of sellers.

The placement of goods is counted from the main elements of the merchandising system. Often the introduction of merchandising begins precisely with the control and analysis of the placement of goods. Product merchandising is as important as brand development, outdoor advertising or promotional promotions. For this reason, merchandising agencies are currently emerging, which provide services to various retailers.

The initial initiative to introduce merchandising abroad came from a wide range of established retailers, consisting of a supermarket chain.

The following advanced methods used in the sale of goods in foreign countries can be used in trade enterprises and organizations of our country:

sale of non-food goods by catalogs at reduced prices in the demonstration hall of retail enterprises;

trading in a limited range of goods with reduced prices in retail enterprises located in the city center and having a strict interior, not more employees to a small shopping area;

"convenience stores", the sale of goods in a limited assortment mainly at trading enterprises that trade in new food products and provide customers with services for a whole day;

increase sales apthomas in order to prevent and absorb Time from the frustrating situations that arise in the sales process in retail stores.

The ways that ensure the success of advanced methods used in the sale of goods at trade enterprises of foreign countries are considered to be the provision of even more different services to the buyer and lowering the price for goods. It is advisable to use these at Trading Enterprises.

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